

Facilitated Genome Editing as Responsible Research and Innovation

Data Management Plan

Creator: Pedro Ramos^{1,2}, Yulia Karimova³, Anna Olsson^{1,2}

Affiliation: ¹- i3S-IBMC, University of Porto

²- ICBAS, University of Porto

³- INESC-TEC, University of Porto

ORCID:

Pedro Ramos (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3389-1682>),

Yulia Karimova (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1015-6709>),

Anna Olsson (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4369-8723>)

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Project abstract:

This project is part of a European Consortium with the aim to improve the genome editing efficiency of CRISPR by research training of 8 Early Stage Researchers (doctoral students) to unleash the full potential of this technology. This DMP refers specifically to one of the doctoral projects, for which the objectives are to address genome editing in the context of Responsible Research and Innovation. In order to achieve this, the overall project intends to reflect on the ethical, legal, social and scientific challenges posed by genome editing by collecting the arguments of renowned experts in the field of biomedicine, animal science, ethics and policy makers. This is done by interviewing these experts in an in-depth format - semi-structured interviews - where points-of-view, reflections and opinions will be collected and which are valuable to understand the present and future potential, limitations and challenges of the genome editing technology and more specifically, CRISPR-Cas9 biotechnology. The interviews will be analysed to understand ethical, legal, social and scientific questions concerning the facilitated use of genome editing in the context of fundamental and applied research within applications that cover the field of humans, animals and crops. In total, we interview 44-45 specialists in an average timeframe of 1-3h in total each using an interview guide that has been built and improved over the 3 years of the project with the help of the research team and external experts in the field of sociology and policy-making. Moreover, the project has been granted approval from the Ethical commission of the Institute of Biomedical Sciences Abel Salazar - University of Porto (CETI ICBAS-UP) as well as all the documentation that will be mentioned in this DMP.

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1. Description of Data:

Data collected in this project are arguments, points-of-view, opinions and reflections from professionals linked to genome editing research either in fundamental or applied fields of research and experts in the fields of ethics, bioethics and policy-makers linked to the assessment of Science and Technology mainly in the field of genetic modification. This data results from semi-structured interviews which will yield audio records that will be transcribed a posteriori and analyzed through content and thematic analysis processes. The raw data consist of audio records that will be transcribed, whereas transcripts are part of the processed data without being analysed. The analysed data take the form of text excerpts that will ultimately convey emergent themes that will answer our most prevalent research questions. The results will be published in research articles without the identification of the participants after a process of pseudonymization that will happen at the pre-analysis stage.

This project objective is to predict the harm-risk/benefit of improving the efficiency of genome editing by obtaining a more detailed knowledge about how genome editing and the different applications in its respect are seen by professionals and experts in science who use these genome editing technologies as well as to map ethics and policy makers views about it. The project's objectives aim to obtain an in-depth knowledge of the genome editing potential and the possible obstacles inherent to it at the scientific, ethical, social and legal level through interviews with experts on the subject of genome editing. The dissemination of this data aims to have an impact in research in the field of life sciences and health, in the pharmaceutical industry and genetics as well as in the drafting of guidelines by policy makers on the use of genome editing which will ultimately have consequences for the general population in the context of health.

During the project the following types of data will be collected and created:

- Qualitative data on points of view and arguments regarding the potential, challenges and limitations associated with genome editing through scientific/technical, ethical and legal perspectives.
- Audio records during interviews.
- Opinions of professionals who are linked to the genome editing area either because they did fundamental or applied research with genome editing technology;
- Opinions of ethicists, bioethicists and policy-makers that are or have been involved in the assessment of Science and Technology biotechnologies with a higher relevance if in the genome editing, genetic engineering or genomics research by participation in institutional and national ethics committees, regulatory/policy or ethics working groups and similar
- Other types of data created during the project (e-mail, agreements, etc.).

These data will be in format:

- Audio records (.mp3 or .aac or wav) .
- Subsequent transcription in text (.txt or .doc).
- Others: .pdf, .xls, .csv and etc.

The data will have relevance in at least the following three ways:

- 1) For the authors - Collected and processed data will be important for further analysis proceeding publication;

- 2) For reviewers/editors and readers - Data will be available for peer-review in case of request;
- 3) For partners of the project - Preservation of data files will be relevant in case any check from the partners of the project and funding entities.

2. Data collection / generation:

Data is collected through semi-structured interviews with audio recordings using an interview guide with a set of questions about participants' thoughts, opinions, points of view and arguments on the topic at hand. The interviews in English include question/answer conversation with specialists in the field of genome editing who are responsible for laboratory groups or have expertise with the technology, experts in ethics, and policy makers. Interviewees will address limitations, potential and impact of genome editing technology. The interviews do not include questions that can identify a person, so no personal data is collected. The part of the data that is sensitive refers only to "philosophical convictions" that interviewees present during interviews. The interviews are carried out by Skype or zoom with a duration of 1 hour and 30 minutes (approximately 44-45 respondents between biomedical researchers, animal scientists and ethicists/policy makers). Camera will be on during the interview, but video recordings collected will be erased permanently right after the interview keeping only the audio records until analysis is completed. Also, during the interview, interviewees are asked to perform some exercises in order to stimulate reflection and bring out important information. Examples of this are exercises where interviewees will order hypothetical applications according to what they think is more realistic and desirable. All information is stored for later transcription and analysis.

All interviews are accompanied by an Informed Consent signed by participants before the interviews. The Ethics Committee of Abel Salazar Institute of Biomedical Sciences (ICBAS) also granted approval for the interviews to take place with life sciences researchers in the first phase and with ethicists and policy makers in the second phase.

All excerpts of text that will be included in the publication as citation will be cross-checked with the initial audio recordings in order to eliminate potential errors or misunderstandings. So, in other words, this procedure is a type of quality control of data.

3. Data management, documentation and curation:

3.1 Managing, storing and curating data

This project is involved in the RRI (Responsible, Research and Innovation) context and responds to all existing requirements related to the Open Science, Research Data Management and Protection of Personal Data. The work takes place at i3S, following ethics approval for data collection and analysis by the Ethics Committee of the Abel Salazar Institute of Biomedical Sciences (ICBAS) where the first author is enrolled as a PhD student.

After the data collection phase, the RAW data is pseudonymized, transcribed and used only to guarantee the data analysis phase. Moreover, the audio records are pseudonymized without reference to the identity of the interviewee, neither in the recorded content nor in the transcript file. The assignment of a reference tag is performed manually. The RAW data will be maintained until the analysis of the interviews is finished, being destroyed as soon as this phase is finished. For this reason, only the dataset of final analysis will be made available and shared with others.

The RAW data will be stored on a personal computer with access only by Pedro Ramos and Anna Olsson until destruction. During the project, Maria Strecht will also have access to this data by sharing the NVivo files and subsequent passwords. The RAW data will not be preserved and will be destroyed as soon as possible after their transcription and analysis. The RAW data will not be shared with anyone else besides people mentioned above.

The transcripts will be stored on a personal computer and an external device (USB stick) with access only by Pedro Ramos, Anna Olsson in first place and later with Maria Strecht in a final stage. These data will be preserved on an external disk that will be bought later or in an internal server in an encrypted format as soon as i3S provides one. These data can be available to anybody by request directly from the authors. Pedro Ramos will be responsible for giving access to these data.

Annotations on paper print-outs of transcript data will be used during the qualitative analysis. As soon as this information has been incorporated into digital processed documents, the paper documents will be destroyed

The processed data of the final analysis will be stored and preserved on an external disk or in an internal server in an encrypted format as soon as i3S provides one. Moreover, processed data for dissemination will be published in a research data repository that will be defined later (i3S website, University of Porto Repository, Magazines for data-paper, another website or data repository like Zenodo), with the specific license that will be defined later and described in an updated version of this DMP.

The expected data size for preservation will be around 10-15GB.

3.2 Metadata standards and data documentation

The RAW data are not accompanied by metadata. For processed data, the metadata standard Dublin Core and Data Documentation Initiative will be used in order to describe and give context to the data.

Project documents include:

- Project Proposal;
- Informed Consents;
- Electronic messages;
- Ethics Committee agreement;
- NVivo files (.rtf files - transcripts);
- Documents with analysis.

3.3 Data preservation strategy and standards

The transcripts and processed data of the final analysis will be preserved during the 5 years on an external disk or in an internal server in an encrypted format if available. The transcripts will be available upon request, processed data of the final analysis will be published in a research data repository without any restriction.

Other project documents like digitalized informed consents, NVivo analysis files as well as the .rtf files generated and exported through NVivo, electronic messages will also be preserved with a preservation time still to be defined.

Backups of the RAW data will not be performed, but backups of the transcripts and processed data will be stored on an external disk (at the moment is used a personal external disk). The backups will be created once a year, probably (will be defined after external disc acquisition), with periodic checks of the backup copies. All responsables for the project have access to backups.

4. Data security and confidentiality of potentially disclosive personal information:

During the project, only Pedro Ramos, Anna Olsson have access to RAW data and transcripts. These RAW data will be destroyed after analysis and transcript data will be preserved on an external disk or in an internal server in an encrypted format if i3S is able to provide one. The transcript data will be available to all responsible for the project and will be available to others upon request directly from authors.

Annotations on paper print-outs of transcript data will be used during the qualitative analysis. As soon as this information has been incorporated into digital processed documents, the paper documents will be destroyed.

Since interviews do not include questions that can identify a person, RAW data (that does not include video, but voice) and transcripts will not be accessible by other people than project collaborators, the guide questions and DMP will be verified by the ethics committee, the DMP will be accepted by all members of the project, and all possible methods for data protection will be applied, there are not many risks relative to data security. They will also have a short lifespan since they will be destroyed after data analysis is completed. All changes related to the data security need to be approved by the PI of the project Anna Olsson and the data responsible researcher, Pedro Ramos.

The risks will also be diminished by using several operating systems, such as Windows 10 Pro and applications, such as Excel, Word, Adobe Reader, with valid licenses. All the computers have properly updated antivirus software which also reduces the risk of intruders.

The browsers have Adblock installed that permit blocking the pop-up pages and other insecure connections. All technical issues related to the software will be controlled by each member of the project and in case of necessary support, they contact the IT staff of the responsible entity. The name of the person will be added in a further version of DMP.

5. Data sharing and access

The RAW data will not be published and shared, due to sensitive and personal information. Transcripts, on the other hand, can be made available by request directly from the authors.

The processed data of the final analysis will be published and shared on the repository that will be defined later without any restrictions but with the specific license that will be defined later. These data will only be available for possible reuse at the end of the project and will be available indefinitely.

Each published dataset of the project will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) assigned by the chosen research data repository to make datasets more findable, accessible and reusable by others. Some research data repositories have curators that can help make the data according to FAIR principles.

6. Responsibilities

The Marie-Curie action partners Pedro Ramos (IBMC-i3S; ICBAS), Cord Brakebusch (University of Copenhagen); Maria Strecht Almeida (ICBAS); Anna Olsson (i3S; ICBAS)), The Institute for Research and Innovation in Health (i3S) and the Abel Salazar Institute of Biomedical Sciences of the University of Porto (ICBAS) are responsible for this project and so the costs are covered by the previously approved funding entity. IBMC-i3S will be the owner of the data in a shared responsibility with the research team described previously. Thus, the

costs of making the dataset deposit and the resources subsequently needed to make the dataset publicly available are included in the project costs. Those responsible for the project will also be responsible for data management, namely:

Responsible for the collection of the data: Pedro Ramos

Responsible for the processing and preservation of the data: Pedro Ramos, Anna Olsson; Maria Strecht; Cord Brakebusch

Responsible for backups: Pedro Ramos, Anna Olsson, IT person in charge (tbd)

Responsible for publishing and sharing data: Pedro Ramos, Maria Strecht Almeida, Anna Olsson

Responsible for DMP creation: Pedro Ramos (pedro.ramos@ibmc.up.pt) and Yulia Karimova (ylaleo@gmail.com) and Anna Olsson (olsson@ibmc.up.pt)

All partners of the project need to agree with the DMP created and rules defined therein.

7. Relevant policies

The informed consent contains an explanation that the interviewee signs only if he or she agrees to participate voluntarily in the study. Moreover, it mentions and guarantees the elimination of audio records as soon as the analysis is finished as well as it guarantees the confidentiality of the collected data. Furthermore, it guarantees that the audio records do not refer to the identity of the interviewees and that the personal data will not become public. Data - with the exception of consents - referring to the interviewee's identity is not shared, nor is it transferred to third parties who can access or view it. No database will be created that contains the identity of the interviewees. The data collected in the audio records have a predefined lifetime and should be deleted when the analysis is completed.